

FLEXIBLE METADATA ANNOTATION FOR AGENT-BASED ENERGY SYSTEM MODELS

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Summary

We introduce a comprehensive and flexible way of metadata annotation for agent-based energy system models using FAME [1]. This approach allows to annotate modelling components, model instances, and model data with metadata. Provided metadata are used to automatically generate metadata summaries for model output. Our implementation is agnostic to the metadata structure and can thus be applied following any standard, e.g., the OEMetadata template [2] or the CodeMeta standard [3]. It applies to both the metadata annotations and the generated metadata summary files.

FAME-io itself is part of the modelling framework [FAME](#). FAME-io reads human-readable input files and compiles a binary representation to be forwarded to the simulation execution software FAME-Core [4]. Human-readable results can be extracted using FAME-io again from the simulation output binaries. Hence, the original simulation input can be recovered. Each step of the workflow shown in Fig. 1 can now be enriched with metadata, thus enabling maximum transparency of modelling with the FAME framework.

Figure 1: Metadata in the FAME workflow

Statement of need

Metadata are critical for the long-term organization, retrieval, and interpretation of data across diverse domains [5]. They provide essential context for researchers by describing the attributes, structure, and provenance of data. By standardizing information, metadata ensure interoperability and enable effective data management practices. As a result, usability and data integrity are improved [6].

This is especially important for the reproducibility of complex scientific workflows, see, e.g., [7] and modelling results, yet significant barriers remain [8]. Metadata annotation of scientific models, however, has increasingly gained traction, especially after various reproducibility crises [5]. First standardisation attempts have been made, e.g., from [3], or [9], however, these metadata do not suffice to fully describe models and their workflows. In the energy systems domain, only a small fraction of the models provide even these basic metadata. At the time of writing, 17 out of 115 open source models registered on the [Open Energy Platform](#) provide a `CITATION.cff` file. and none feature a `codemeta.json` file. To the best of our knowledge, no model includes a complete set of metadata annotations of inputs, outputs, and modelling components like we demonstrate below.

The presented approach enables modellers to comprehensively annotate FAME-based models, their components, and model configurations with metadata and to reuse these metadata when describing model results. This allows preserving model-specific information within the generated data sets and thus strengthens modelling transparency and result explainability. In particular, our flexible approach does not put any constraints on the metadata structure, allowing to satisfy domain-specific needs on a per-model basis, important for transferability [7]. While the presented work is not directly applicable to other modelling frameworks, we provide an instructive example and template on how metadata can be easily integrated in modelling workflows. With it, we hope to pave the road of comprehensive metadata annotation for other scientific models and tools.

Metadata annotation

With FAME-Io all aspects of models and inputs are described using [YAML](#) files. YAML allows creating complex data structures from lists, key-value dictionaries, and scalars values. Since [release 3.5](#) of FAME-Io every model aspect can be annotated with metadata. To this end, FAME-Io reserves the keyword `metadata` that can be added to any element that is a dictionary (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Example on how to add metadata annotations to mappings, scalars, and lists

All content below the metadata keyword is then automatically associated with the dictionary. To annotate a scalar, it is first transformed into a dictionary by associating the scalar with the reserved keyword `value`. Then, the metadata keyword, can be used to add metadata to the scalar. In a similar way, lists

can be annotated by transforming them in a dictionary, this time placing the list elements below the reserved keyword *values*. To increase robustness, FAME-Io uses cases-insensitive keyword detection.

In order to extract and store metadata annotations from every model configuration element, FAME-Io classes and data structures were enhanced. All data structures inherit an abstract base class Metadata that automatically extracts input under the keyword `metadata` and injects the stored metadata when the data structures are exported. This enables metadata description of agent classes, their attributes, and output columns on the model level. In addition, each scenario, each agent instance, and each input value can be annotated on the execution level. The structure of all FAME-Io input files is fully described in its [documentation](#).

Since no metadata standard for the annotation of models in the energy systems domain exists yet, we decided not to restrict the structure of the metadata. Thus, any content can be placed below the metadata keyword. Once standards evolve, implementing tools to check the compatibility of metadata annotations will be considered. Adapting to a standard should then be easy, given that just the terms below metadata sections have to be refactored.

Automatic metadata summary

FAME-Io creates a *metadata.json* file describing the extracted simulation outputs. Previously provided input and model metadata are used in this process. Again, no standard for metadata description of model results has been established so far, but the [OEMetadata template](#) is congruent in that respect. Therefore, FAME-Io provides a template compatible with the OEMetadata specifications. FAME-Io's templating engine, however, allows defining the structures for the created metadata file - and which sections of metadata to use from the model metadata.

Figure 3: Relation between model metadata, metadata template, and output metadata files

As illustrated in Fig. 3 the templating engine will search for replacement statements (indicated by angle brackets) in the template and then try to locate the information in the original model or input metadata. Since FAME-Io creates an individual output file per type of agent, agent-specific metadata can be matched to these files using the keyword (*agent*). Similarly, metadata specific to a column within an output file can be matched with the column section using the keyword (*column*). Iteration statements in the template enable covering any number of agents and output columns without redundancy in the template. This allows a slim and generalisable definition of model output metadata templates without requiring knowledge of the actual model structure. The [FAME-Io documentation](#) in detail covers which metadata are used by the provided OEMetadata template, and how own templates can be defined.

Example application

We provide a fully-fledged example of metadata annotation for the electricity market model AMIRIS [10] in the repository [AMIRIS-Examples](#). Model components have been fully annotated regarding their inputs, outputs, and capabilities. Wherever available, the closest concepts in the Open Energy Ontology, see [11], are provided. Every output of the model is fully described by an accompanying metadata file. Extracting the metadata and compiling the output metadata file has a negligible impact on the total runtime of the FAME-Io routines. The additional data amount to a few kilobytes for our example scenarios.

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